

Crosslinking Hagfish Intermediate Filament Protein Fiber Bundles with Glutaraldehyde Vapor

Does exposure time and PEO affect the mechanical properties of recombinant hagfish intermediate filament bundles?

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In previous work from our team [[Electrospinning Hagfish Intermediate Filament Protein and Fabrication of Aligned Fiber Bundles](#)], we showed that recombinant hagfish intermediate filament protein (rHIF) can be electrospun into aligned nanofiber mats and rolled into bundles that can withstand mechanical load. Crosslinking those bundles with glutaraldehyde vapor appeared to roughly double their tensile strength when hydrated. We chose 90 minutes as our crosslinking baseline and moved forward with experimentation. That is what this work is aiming to better understand: is 90 minutes the optimal crosslinking time for our hagfish bundles? And if not, what times are better for giving us stronger mechanical properties?

There is also a second question that we're hoping to answer with this experimental study. Our spinning dope contains poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) as a spinnability aid, at a small fraction of the total fiber weight (<2%). The standard protocol removed it by soaking the bundles in DI water for 48 hours (with water replacements and slight agitation) before crosslinking. But what if we reverse the order and crosslink while the PEO is still in the fiber? PEO has terminal hydroxyl groups and oxygen atoms in the backbone that may react with or become physically locked into the crosslinked protein network and may not be rinsed out.

This experiment hopes to tease out the answer to two things: (1) what is our optimal crosslinking time for the best mechanical properties of our fiber bundles? And (2) how does the presence of PEO impact the resultant tensile strength of our bundles?

A bit of background on the chemistry

Hagfish intermediate filament proteins are rich in the amino acid lysine. Glutaraldehyde is a dialdehyde that reacts with primary amine (specifically the ϵ -amine on lysine) to form Schiff base linkages. These are covalent bonds and permanently crosslink protein chains together at those sites. The vapor-phase keeps the process gentle and relatively uniform across the length of the bundle, however because it is a vapor-phase process, there is expected to be some impact from the diffusion of the aldehyde vapor from the outside to the internal core of the bundle.

The expectation going into the time series was straightforward: more time means more crosslinks, more crosslinks means a stiffer and stronger network, giving a higher mechanical strength but possibly a loss of the extensibility. Whether there is a saturation point, where all the accessible lysine residues have reacted and additional exposure does nothing, was also an open question we hoped to learn about as well.

How we made and tested the bundles

Recombinant hagfish intermediate filament proteins were provided by Prof. Justin Jones at Utah State University. We dissolved the protein at 15 wt% in an 85:15 HFIP:formic acid solvent system with 0.25 wt% PEO (1000 kg/mol, Sigma-Aldrich) added as a spinnability aid. The mixed solvent system slows evaporation during fiber formation, which helps produce more consistent fiber morphology. Dopes were stirred for 3 hours before spinning and used within 6 hours of preparation. Electrospinning was done on a StonyLab commercial system at 10 kV, 0.01 mL/min flow rate, 20 cm tip-to-collector distance, 20-gauge needle, and 3000 rpm drum speed. The chamber sat at 19.5 to 20.5°C and 52% relative humidity throughout. After spinning, the mats were removed from the drum collector and dried overnight at room temperature to drive off any residual solvent.

Bundles were made by rolling the mats perpendicular to the fiber direction until a roughly cylindrical geometry formed, with fibers running axially along the bundle length. The target diameter was in the 400 to 600 μm range, with some variability expected given the manual process. For the standard crosslinking, we soaked the rolled bundles in DI water for 48 hours with exchanges every 12 hours to remove the PEO before any crosslinking. For the PEO comparison group, that soaking step was skipped and the bundles went straight into the crosslinking chamber with PEO still present. Crosslinking was done by placing bundles in a sealed glass chamber with a 4 mL vial of 25% glutaraldehyde solution (Sigma-Aldrich) at room temperature for 30, 90, 180, or 360 minutes. After exposure, samples were quenched in 100 mM glycine solution for 10 minutes to cap any unreacted aldehyde groups, rinsed three times in DI water, and stored in DI water until testing.

Bundle diameters were measured from optical micrographs taken on a Keyence laser profilometer and analyzed in ImageJ. We assumed a circular cross-section to calculate the cross-sectional area for stress calculations, though this estimate is likely an oversimplification of the actual bundle diameter. Tensile testing was done on a CellScale Univert with a 2.5 N load cell. All samples were tested in a hydrated state after soaking for at least 24 hours in DI water and used immediately when removed from storage. The strain rate was standardized at 100 mm/min and the engineering stress and strain were calculated from the output force and displacement data from the tool.

Bundle diameters

Below are two images from our laser profilometer comparing the rolled fiber bundles, with data of all measured bundles in Table S1 at the end of this paper. One artifact that immediately stands out is that bundles from the 30-minute group were thinner than other groups, on average around 269 μm in diameters versus 490 to 600 μm for the longer crosslinking time groups and controls. These were rolled from the same mats using the same method, but the process is done by hand, highlighting the natural variability in bundle diameter. This matters because stress scales inversely with cross-sectional area, so any error in measurements can drastically impact the calculated UTS across groups. The average measured diameters of the bundles in this sample available in table S1 at the end of this post.

Figure 1. Optical microscope images of rolled electrospun rHIF fiber bundles. The image on the left was a 30 minute sample and on the right a 180 minute sample, showing the natural variation in bundle diameter from rolling the samples by hand. The scale bar for both images is 400 μ m.

How crosslinking time affects strength and extensibility

Figure 2 below shows the stress-strain curves for all four crosslinking times. Table 2 pulls out the mean UTS and failure strain for each group.

Figure 2. Stress-strain curves for rHIF bundles crosslinked for 30, 90, 180, and 360 minutes, and the uncrosslinked control group.

Table 2. Sample group mechanical properties (mean \pm SD).

Group	n	Mean UTS (MPa)	SD (MPa)	Mean Failure Strain (%)	SD (%)
Control	4	2.54	0.38	217.7	18.5
30 min	3	3.47	0.87	219.0	23.1
90 min	3	2.08	0.22	210.3	34.5
180 min	4	2.31	0.13	242.2	5.9
360 min	4	2.82	0.53	236.5	12.9

The hypothesis going in was that longer crosslinking time would mean higher UTS and potentially lower extensibility. The data does not support that, and I think that is the most interesting result here.

The 30-minute group has the highest mean UTS at 3.47 MPa, but the spread is wide. Sample 30.2 came in at 4.677 MPa while 30.3 was 2.59 MPa, and the thin diameters in this group mean any measurement error in the diameter gets amplified in the stress calculation. The 90-minute group sits below the uncrosslinked controls on UTS (2.04 MPa vs. 2.50 MPa), which was not what we expected at all. One way to read this is that 90 minutes of glutaraldehyde exposure is enough to interfere with the natural load-sharing in the fiber network without adding enough covalent connectivity to compensate, so the net effect is that it disrupts before it reinforces.

From 90 minutes onward, UTS climbs back up through 180 minutes (2.27 MPa) and 360 minutes (2.68 MPa), which does suggest the network is gradually becoming better reinforced with longer exposure. Whether it is approaching saturation at 360 minutes or would continue to improve at longer times is not something we can answer yet, but the recovery from the 90-minute dip is apparent and consistent across samples.

The controls fail at an average of 218% elongation, and the crosslinked groups span 210–242%, a range that largely overlaps with the control. The differences in extensibility across groups are small relative to the within-group variability, and no clear trend with the crosslinking time emerges from the data. The 180-minute group shows the tightest clustering ($242 \pm 6\%$), but even that is only modestly above the control mean and well within the overall spread. The prior report of controls failing at $\sim 112\%$ strain was an artifact of using a hardcoded 30 mm gauge length rather than each sample's actual measured gauge length, which artificially compressed the control strains and exaggerated the apparent effect of crosslinking on extensibility.

Putting it in context with the uncrosslinked controls

Figure 3 displays the control bundles and crosslinked bundles together.

Figure 3. Stress-strain curves for all uncrosslinked control bundles (gray) versus all crosslinked replicates for each time group.

The controls are not weak, in fact, they have an average UTS of 2.50 MPa which reflects the contribution of the aligned fiber architecture. While the previous paper showed a roughly 2x improvement from crosslinking at 90 minutes, in our experiments for this work the 90-minute crosslinked bundles actually land just below the control mean on UTS, with no meaningful difference in extensibility. The 360-minute group shows the best combination of strength recovery and high failure strain.

The difference from what we saw previously is likely batch-to-batch variability in the rolling process and in the glutaraldehyde chamber conditions. Getting tighter control over bundle diameter through automation of the rolling process and ensuring consistent vapor concentration across the chamber are the two means that would improve reproducibility of our results.

Figure 4. UTS vs. Crosslinking time of rHIF bundles. Diamonds = group mean, bars are within 1 SD of the mean, and circles = individual replicates.

Does it matter if PEO is present during crosslinking?

The second question of our experiments was looking to answer the question of whether PEO removal from the bundles is necessary at all. We crosslinked a set of bundles for 180 minutes with glutaraldehyde vapor without first removing the PEO. After crosslinking and a quench in glycine solution, these samples went through the standard 48-hour water soak to remove any unbound PEO, and then were tested identically to other groups. Figure 5 below shows the comparison.

Figure 5. *rHIF-only (orange) versus rHIF+PEO (teal) bundles crosslinked for 180 minutes.*

The mean UTS values are essentially identical: 2.31 MPa on average for rHIF-only bundles and 2.36 MPa for rHIF+PEO bundles. The presence of PEO during crosslinking does not change the peak UTS, and only the extensibility appears to be impacted. The rHIF+PEO group has a mean failure strain of 222.3% compared to 242.2% for the standard rHIF-only 180-minute group, though the variability in the PEO group is about 3x higher. One possible understanding of the result is that some PEO is physically or covalently incorporated into the crosslinked network and with protein-protein connectivity and elastic properties, the network's ability to stretch before failure is limited. The plan is to use Raman spectroscopy to look for residual PEO in the crosslinked-then-soaked bundles by tracking the C-O-C stretch at approximately 1100 cm^{-1} .

Conclusions

The crosslinking time series did not confirm the hypothesis that longer exposure time monotonically increases tensile strength. Instead, strength dips at 90 minutes before recovering at 180 and 360 minutes. The 30-minute samples had the highest mean UTS but also the thinnest diameters and the most variability, so we are cautious about reading too much into that result without repeating it with better diameter control. The extensibility was similar across all groups, with failure strains ranging from 210-242% across crosslinked groups and 218% for the controls, suggesting crosslinking has little effect on how far the bundles can stretch until failure.

On the PEO question, crosslinking with PEO still within the rHIF network does not change peak strength, and its presence in the crosslinked network may in fact limit extensibility. Whether that is a material effect from residual PEO or a structural effect from how the network forms with PEO present is still open for further studies. Future Raman characterization will

hopefully help answer this question.

These results are suggestive but not conclusive. The sample sizes are small ($n = 3-4$ per group), the bundle diameters vary within and across groups due to the hand-rolling process, and we have only one crosslinking time point in common with our previous work. The non-monotonic UTS pattern is an interesting finding, but the 30-minute result in particular rests on three samples with wide spread and thin diameters, and should be treated cautiously until it can be repeated with better diameter control. The PEO comparison points towards a small effect on extensibility, with the mechanism still unresolved but future plans for characterizing the system and improving our fundamental understanding. What we can say with confidence is that 90 minutes is not an optimal crosslinking time for this system by any metric we measured, and that longer exposures appear to give more consistent and stronger results, but don't offer a strong reason for being in place in the first place due to the additional time sink of the extra processing step.

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Supplementary data

Table S1. Measured bundle diameters for all samples.

Control.1	430.45
Control.2	493.65
Control.3	499.03
Control.4	495.61
30.1	261.44
30.2	266.57
30.3	279.60
90.1	631.78
90.2	615.42
90.3	547.24
180.1	466.19
180.2	531.62
180.3	490.15
180.4	469.03
360.1	502.02

360.2	516.80
360.3	536.97
360.4	326.04
PEO180.1	565.35
PEO180.2	366.98
PEO180.3	524.66
PEO180.4	540.48